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Sustainable Cellulose-Based Coatings and Their Impact on Mechanical and Barrier Properties of Paper

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ABSTRACT

The fabrication of cellulose-based barrier paper by coating base paper with regenerated cellulose is presented. Various concentrations of cellulose solutions and coating weights, akin to conventional polymeric coatings, are employed. The coated papers' properties, including morphological changes, mechanical properties, and barrier properties, are evaluated and compared to the reference base paper. It is observed that cellulose concentrations of 6 and 9 wt.% in the coating solution provide good paper coverage, evidenced by a reduction in porosity. The oxygen barrier properties surpass those typically achieved with laminated/extruded polyolefins or cellulose esters. Additionally, enhanced grease barrier properties against hot oil are attained. The tensile indices of the coated papers decrease, likely due to the wetting and redrying process during coating. However, the strain at break shows a slight improvement, and no significant difference is noted in the tear index compared to the reference.

1 | Introduction

Increasing awareness of environmental impacts and tightening legislation are driving the packaging industry to transition from petroleum-based materials to bio-based or biodegradable options [1, 2]. These alternatives include petroleum-derived biodegradable plastics such as polybutylene succinate and polyvinyl alcohol [3], biomass-based non-biodegradable plastics like biomass polyethylene, and biomass-based biodegradable plastics such as polylactic acid, and starch [4–8]. Other alternatives include cellulosic packaging solutions such as board and flexible papers [1].

Despite their widespread use, cellulosic materials often contain petroleum-based components, such as polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate, waxes, and latex to control moisture and gas properties [1, 9]. Traditional methods of applying these coatings involve dispersion coatings with emulsions,

using adhesives to bond laminated filmic structures, or extrusion coating molten plastics onto the cellulosic surface [10, 11]. New bio-based coating alternatives necessitate changes in application techniques, such as solution coating or curtain coating [2, 12]. Research on biopolymer-based coatings is ongoing to find alternatives and to develop new procedures. Various forms of cellulosic materials, including nanocelluloses and cellulose derivatives, have been extensively studied [13–16], but challenges remain regarding processability, costs, and dewatering [17, 18]. One proposed solution is to create a pure cellulosic composite with good barrier properties through coating using regenerated cellulose [9, 19, 20].

Regenerated cellulose, derived from dissolving and regenerating natural cellulose, gains film-forming characteristics along with certain functionalities, e.g., in terms of gas barrier [21]. Solvent systems like alkali solution, ionic liquids, and amine oxides such as N-methyl morpholine-N-oxide (NMMO) are typically used for

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cellulose dissolution [20, 22, 23]. There are already examples in the literature of applying regenerated cellulose coatings to paper. Zhang et al. [20] developed a regenerated cellulose coating by applying a 0.5 mm thick alkaline cellulose solution onto paper, resulting in dry paper with 2 to 20 wt.% regenerated cellulose. The mechanical properties improved significantly, particularly in the cross-linked samples. Papers coated with 20 wt.% cross-linked cellulose achieved a tensile strength of 75 MPa, compared to 20 MPa for untreated paper, and elongation increased from 3% to 10%. The coated papers also demonstrated good oxygen barrier properties and increased resistance to greases. Krzysztof et al [9]. coated paper with cellulose dissolved in NMMO, resulting in surface-coated paper or a composite-like structure, depending on the treatment method. Heat-treated, composite-type samples showed significant improvements in tensile properties and elongation, while surface-coated samples had the best air barrier properties. In another study by Zhu et al. [19]. it was reported that paper coated with cellulose dissolved in an ionic liquid had superior mechanical and oxygen barrier properties. Coatings with 2 and 4 wt.% cellulose solution increased smoothness, while a 6 wt.% solution resulted in uneven surfaces due to high viscosity. The 2 wt.% cellulose coating provided significant oxygen barrier protection due to compact packing between the regenerated cellulose and base paper fibers. In a recent study by Du et al. [24], it was demonstrated that ultra-thin coatings using cellulose dissolved in NMMO reduced paper porosity, air permeability, oxygen transmission rate, and Cobb value. Modifying substrate paper properties through beating/refining positively affected barrier properties. Mechanical improvements were higher for non-beaten or slightly beaten pulp, with performance stabilizing in more processed materials.

Building on previous research [9, 19, 20, 24], this study explores the application of cellulose coatings on commercial kraft paper using the rod coating method. Earlier studies [9, 20, 24] demonstrated the potential of regenerated cellulose to enhance paper's barrier performance, but were mostly limited to laboratory sheets and filter paper, which differ from commercial-grade paper that undergoes industrial finishing processes like calendaring [25, 26]. In this study, the rod coating method was chosen for its well-established nature and its ability to provide better control over the coating thickness [10]. Many of the earlier studies [9, 19, 20] did not discuss the effect of coating thickness on paper performance, or only used a single coating thickness. This study investigates cellulose solutions from 2 to 9 wt.%, using various rod types to determine the optimal coating amount for effective barrier properties. It evaluates the effects of cellulose coating on paper's grammage, thickness, and morphology (including SEM imaging and porosity). Additionally, the mechanical properties (tensile strength, elongation, and burst strength) and barrier properties (air, oxygen, and grease resistance) were evaluated. This research aims to provide insights into the performance of new biobased and biodegradable cellulosic coatings on commercial paper, contributing to sustainable packaging materials development. It also offers an industrially applicable strategy for creating sustainable and biodegradable materials, addressing scalability limitations of some solvents used in previous studies [27].

TABLE 1 | The coating amount was controlled using three different rods.

Rod type	Wire diameter (mm)	Theoretical wet film deposit (μm)
A	0.08	6
B	0.30	24
C	0.64	50

2 | Experimental Section

2.1 | Preparation of Coating Solutions

The coating solutions were prepared by dissolving pretreated softwood kraft pulp from UPM Kaukas pulp mill, Finland, in an alkaline solvent at concentrations of 2, 4, 6, and 9 wt.% to solvent.

2.2 | Paper Coating

A commercial kraft paper, Solide Lucent (UPM, Finland), with a basis weight of 45 g/m² was used as the substrate. The coating process was carried out using rod coating (RK Printcoat Industries K303S Multicoater, United Kingdom) with three rods wound with wires of different diameters to control the thickness of the coating and the amount of wet film deposited (Table 1).

Approximately 40 mL of the coating solution was applied to the leading edge of the paper and spread using a constant rod at a speed of 1 m/min. The coated samples were then sequentially immersed in a 10 wt.% sulfuric acid regeneration bath, a reverse osmosis water bath for rinsing, and finally a 25 wt.% glycerol plasticizer bath, each for about 10 s. After this chemical treatment, the samples were air-dried at room temperature for 24 h. Sulfuric acid (95%, VWR Chemicals, Belgium) served as the regenerating agent, while glycerol ($\geq 97\%$, VWR Chemicals, Belgium) was used as the plasticizer.

2.3 | Paper Grammage and Thickness

The thicknesses of the coated samples and reference papers were measured according to ISO 534:2011 using a micrometer (Lorentzen & Wettre Micrometer 51D, Sweden). The coating thickness was approximated by subtracting the thickness of the base paper from the thickness of the coated sample. The grammage of the samples was measured according to ISO 536:2019 using the analytical balance (Mettler Toledo AG204, Switzerland). For this measurement, pre-conditioned (23°C, 50% relative humidity (RH)) samples, stacks of five test pieces, each cut to 141 × 141 mm, were measured simultaneously. The coating grammage was approximated by subtracting the grammage of the base paper from that of the coated samples.

2.4 | Microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (Hitachi SU5000 FE-SEM, Japan) was used to image the surfaces of selected samples at

magnifications of 100×, 500×, and 1300×. Prior to imaging, the samples were coated with a 4 nm layer of platinum using a sputter coater. An accelerating voltage of 3.0 kV, working distances of 7.3–8.2 mm, and a secondary electron detector were used. Three parallel images were taken for each sample at each magnification.

2.5 | Paper Porosity

Porosity was measured using a BEKK instrument (Messmer Büchel Automatic BEKK Smoothness & Porosity Tester 58-05, USA) equipped with a specific porosity measuring head that allows air to pass through the sample. A small chamber with a volume of 38 mL (1/10 of the total volume) was chosen, and a pressure range of −50.66 kPa to −48.00 kPa was selected to allow 1 mL of air to pass through the sample. Eight parallel measurements were taken, and the results were recorded in BEKK seconds, which were then converted to microliters of air per second.

2.6 | Spectroscopy

The FTIR spectrum of the papers was measured in the wavelength range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} (Shimadzu IRTracer-100) using the single reflection ATR accessory (Shimadzu QATR10).

2.7 | Mechanical Properties

Tensile parameters, including tensile index and strain at break, were determined according to ISO 1924-3:2005 using an L&W Tensile Tester SE 064. Samples of 15 mm × 180 mm were fastened between two pneumatic clamps positioned 100 mm apart. One clamp was connected to a force sensor and remained stationary, while the other pulled the sample horizontally at a constant elongation rate of 100 mm min^{-1} . Ten parallel measurements were taken.

The tear index was measured according to ISO 1974:2012 using an L&W Tearing Tester 009. Pre-slit samples, cut into 50 × 62 mm pieces, were torn in half perpendicular to the plane along the length of the sample using a swinging pendulum. Four parallel stacks of four test sheets were measured.

The puncture resistance measurements were conducted according to the SFS-EN 14477:2004 standard, using the universal testing machine (Shimadzu AGS-X 10 kN, Japan) equipped with Trapezium X software. A sharp probe, with a diameter of 0.8 mm and a tip radius of 0.4 mm, was used to puncture five parallel test pieces at a speed of 100 mm min^{-1} .

2.8 | Heptane Vapor Transmission Rate and Oxygen Transmission Rate

Heptane vapor transmission rate (HVTR) was measured using a gravimetric method, adapted from Gaudreault et al. [28], where three parallel circular test pieces, under controlled experimental conditions (23°C, 50% RH), were placed barrier-side inward in aluminum test cups containing 7 mL of n-heptane on a foam pad

and sealed with molten wax using a sealing mold. The sealed cups were weighed at regular intervals (0, 2, 3, 5, and 25 h after sealing), and HVTR was calculated based on the mass loss over time, expressed as grams of n-heptane per square meter per day ($\text{g/m}^2\text{d}$).

Oxygen transmission rate (OTR) of the samples was measured according to ISO 15105-2:2003 (OxySense 8101e Oxygen Permeation Analyser, Systech Illinois, USA), under controlled experimental conditions (23°C, 50% RH). Two parallel test pieces of 4 × 4 cm in size were measured.

2.9 | Grease Barrier

Grease resistance of the coated samples was determined according to ISO 16532-1:2008. Four parallel samples were cut into 141 × 141 mm pieces, with two perpendicular 180° folds made to form a cross-pattern in the center of each sample. Approximately 3 mL of red-colored palm kernel oil, tempered to 55°C, was poured onto the samples, covering a circular area 9 cm in diameter from the center of the cross-fold. A disc of absorbent paper was placed on top of the oil, and the samples were heated in a 55°C oven for 20 min. After heating, excess oil was removed, and the samples were inspected for signs of oil permeance. These signs appeared on the reverse side of the paper as more intensely colored areas compared to the light pink hue visible from the application side. Conclusions on grease resistance were based on the presence or absence of permeated oil and the sizes of the permeated areas.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Effects of Coating on Paper Grammage and Morphology

Figure 1a illustrates the amount of dry coating applied to the paper surface. As observed, the coating amount varied between 12 and 26 g m^{-2} , depending on the rod sizes and cellulose concentrations used. These coating amounts corresponded to a 26% to 57% increase in paper grammage. This was higher than the amounts previously reported, coating amounts of 0.09 to 20 wt.% on dry paper [20, 24]. Nevertheless, the coating amounts used in the current study were comparable to those of traditional plastics. For instance, commercially used polyethylene coatings typically had a coating grammage of around 15–25 g/m^2 [29]. In comparison to bio-based coatings, such as PLA coatings, coating weight of 2–90 g/m^2 had been reported for paperboard [30].

As shown in Figure 1a, with 2 wt.% cellulose, the deposited coating remained nearly constant across all rods, indicating that this solution was too liquid-like to fully control the amount, leading to poor loading of the rod. At higher cellulose concentrations of 6 and 9 wt.%, which were more viscous, the coating amount increased with the rod type. When using the rod A, the deposited amount was $\leq 16 \text{ g/m}^2$, and the coating amount remained almost the same regardless of the cellulose concentration. With rod B, there was no significant difference in the amount of coating deposited on the paper surface compared to rod A at low cellulose concentrations of 2 and 4 wt.%, but the difference increased with higher cellulose concentrations. The highest coating amounts

FIGURE 1 | (a) Amount of coating (g/m²) using different rods and cellulose concentrations (b) increase in paper thickness (µm) after coating.

FIGURE 2 | (a) Uncoated, and coated paper with (b) 2 wt.%, (c) 4 wt.%, (d) 6 wt.% and (e) 9 wt.% cellulose (f) The porosity of the of the paper using different cellulose concentrations and rods in comparison to reference. The porosity of the reference base paper is shown using a red dotted line.

were achieved with rod C. Figure 1b shows that the coating increased the thickness of the papers by 14–22 µm, corresponding to a 34%–53% increase from the original thickness. These values were similar to those reported in the literature for biopolymeric coatings [10, 30, 31].

Figure 2 presents the SEM images of uncoated (a,b) and coated papers (c–f) using rod C. As the cellulose concentration in the coating increased, the network structure of the uncoated paper became progressively covered. At cellulose concentrations of 2 wt.% and 4 wt.% (coating weights of approximately 14–20 g/m²), the interconnected fiber network structure remained visible. However, at cellulose concentrations of 6 and 9 wt.% (coating weights of approximately 20–25 g/m²), the individual fibers were completely covered by the coating. This visual observation was supported by BEKK porosity measurements, which showed a significant decrease in porosity (95–98%) for paper coated with 6 wt.% and 9 wt.% cellulose solutions (Figure 2f). For uncoated paper, the porosity was 13 µL s⁻¹, whereas for coated samples with 6 and 9 wt.% cellulose, it ranged from 0.7 to 0.2 µL s⁻¹. With 2 wt and 4 wt.% cellulose content in the coating, the porosity gradually decreased with increasing rod size. Previous research [19] had already reported that some fiber outlines could still be detected when the based paper was coated with 2 wt.% cellulose concentration, while the surface of coated paper became much smoother when coated with 4 wt.% cellulose concentration.

However, as different solvent systems were used the cellulose concentration of 6 wt.% was already too viscous, resulting in an uneven surface. The presence of the cellulosic coating was also evident in the FTIR spectra, which revealed a transformation of the surface structure from cellulose I to cellulose II. The FTIR spectra for samples coated with a 6 wt.% cellulose solution using rods A, B, and C in comparison to reference base paper are provided in the Figure S1 and Table S1.

3.2 | Mechanical Properties

Figure 3a illustrates the tensile indices of the coated papers compared to the reference. As observed, the addition of coating notably decreased the tensile index. This result contradicted previous findings in the literature [9, 19, 20] where the tensile indices of regenerated cellulose-coated papers have been shown to improve significantly. There were several reasons that may have explained this. First, there may have been differences in how the coating solution penetrated the base paper [32]. In this study, it was assumed that the coating remained on the paper surface rather than forming a composite, as the coating was applied directly to the dry pre-coated base paper before being deposited into the regeneration bath. The regeneration and washing techniques caused the paper to swell and reorient, which was detrimental to its mechanical properties [16, 33].

FIGURE 3 | Effect of coating on mechanical properties of the paper: (a) Tensile index, (b) tear index, (c) elongation at break, (d) puncture resistance. The properties of the reference base paper are shown using a red dotted line.

Additionally, the substrate base paper most likely influenced the results. In the previous studies either laboratory hand sheets [19, 24] or filter paper [20] were used as a substrate. The addition of coating layers to these porous substrates may have caused a higher improvement in mechanical properties than on ready-made industrial pre-coated paper, which had already passed through the calendaring process [25, 26].

For tear indices (Figure 3b) no such dramatic decrease due to the coating process was observed, and the values were almost at the same level as the reference. However, with regard to the strain at break (Figure 3c), a slight increase in the elongation was observed, being 1.5% for the reference and approximately 2.5% for the coated samples. This result aligned with the previously reported studies [19, 20] where improvements in elongation of the paper after regenerated cellulose coating were observed.

The puncture resistance (Figure 3d) remained constant in samples coated with cellulose solutions at concentrations of 6 and 9 wt.%. However, a slight decrease was observed with 2 and 4 wt.% cellulose content, especially when rods A and C were used. It was assumed that the paper wetting during the coating process had a slight negative impact on puncture resistance [34], but once enough coating was applied, the effects of the processing were neutralized.

3.3 | Barrier Properties of the Coated Papers

Figure 4a,b show the barrier properties for two different gases: heptane vapor and oxygen. In both cases, there was a notable

improvement in barrier properties, especially when compared to the uncoated base paper. However, the OTR was not as good as previously reported for regenerated cellulose-coated paper in the literature [18, 19]. This suggested that there were still small pinholes in the coating, causing gas leakage. While uncoated paper and paper coated with a 2 wt.% did not exhibit measurable oxygen barrier properties (quantification limit $\leq 60\,000$ cc/m²/day), papers coated with 6 wt.% and 9 wt.% cellulose solutions achieved OTR values 2000 and 8000 cc/m²/day, respectively. This indicates that the oxygen barrier was better than that of cellulose esters (18 000 cc/m²/day) or biopolyethylene (11 000 cc/m²/day) [2]. However, these values are not yet in par with those obtained for PLA or PVA coatings, which had been reported to have OTR values of 300–400 cc/m²/day and 130 cc/m²/day, respectively [2].

Papers coated with 4, 6, and 9 wt.% cellulose solutions achieved HVTR below 20 g/m²/day, compared to the uncoated paper reference, which exhibited a transmission rate of 460 g/m²/day. The values obtained for the coated samples were within the same range as those reported for Polyethylene terephthalate and Polypropylene in the literature [35]. Figure 4b,c shows the results from the grease barrier measurements. As observed, the hot colored oil passed through all the samples within the 20 min measurement period. However, increasing the cellulose concentration in the coating reduced the amount of oil penetration, which was visible as the observed color intensity decreased. Additionally, increasing the coating amount by changing the rod size clearly hinders oil penetration, once again confirming that rod C was the best selection for coating paper with regenerated cellulose.

FIGURE 4 | (a) Heptane vapor and oxygen transmission rates of coated samples, (b) Penetration of colored oil into coated samples with varying cellulose concentrations and rod C, (c) Effect of rod type on hot oil permeability of samples coated with a 6 wt.% cellulose solution.

4 | Conclusions

In this study, regenerated cellulose coating was applied to paper using the rod coating method. Cellulose concentrations of 2 and 4 wt.% were found to have too low viscosity to achieve good coverage and sufficient barrier properties. In contrast, cellulose concentrations of 6 and 9 wt.%, reduced porosity and improved oxygen and grease barrier properties. The use of cellulose solution, followed by regeneration and washing steps, instead of molten polymers, presented some challenges, likely due to the rewetting of the paper, which caused a decrease in tensile indices. Nevertheless, the tear index was unchanged when using higher coating amounts (20–25 g/m²), and a slight improvement in elongation at break was observed. Rod with higher theoretical wet film deposits was proved to be the most effective, for selected cellulose concentrations, in achieving optimal coating amounts and better barrier properties, particularly in reducing oil penetration. These results suggest that regenerated cellulose is a promising coating material, offering an environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic coatings, although the application process still requires some further developments.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: mame70044-sup-0001-SuppMat.docx.